

Automating the response to GDPR's Right of Access

Abstract.

With the enforcement of the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation, users of Web services ('data subjects' under the GDPR), which are powered by the intensive usage of personal data, have seen their rights be incremented, and the same can be said about the obligations imposed on the 'data controllers' responsible for these services. In particular, the 'Right of Access', which gives users the option to obtain a copy of their personal data as well as relevant details such as the categories of personal data being processed or the purposes and duration of said processing, is putting increasing pressure on controllers as their execution often requires a manual response effort, and the wait time is negatively affecting the data subjects. Considering this, controllers would benefit from having the information they need to provide to users, if they wish to exercise such right, in a structured format. In this context, the main goal of this work is the development of an API, which builds on the previously mentioned structured information, to assist controllers in the automation of replies to access requests. The implemented API method is then used in the implementation of a Solid application whose main goal is to assist users in exercising their right of access to data stored in Solid Pods.

Keywords. digital rights management, GDPR, right of access, Solid

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1. Introduction

With the enforcement of the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), users of Web services have seen their rights as GDPR 'data subjects' being expanded when it comes to the processing of their personal data. On the other hand, on top of other GDPR-related obligations, 'data controllers', the entities that effectively process the data, have seen an increase of workload related with the response to data subject's right-related requests. GDPR's Chapter III¹ details a set of 10 data subject rights, starting with the 'Right to be Informed' described in Articles 13 and 14 and ending with the 'Right to object to automated decision making' in Article 22. Considering this, data controllers would benefit from having the information that they need to provide to data subjects in a structured format in order to automate the response to such requests [1]. In

¹<https://gdpr-info.eu/chapter-3/>

particular, the ‘Right of Access’² is putting more and pressure on controllers as they not only have to provide the purpose for which the data is being used or the types of data being processed, but also need to provide a copy of said data. As this task is usually done manually, the wait time can negatively affect data subjects.

In addition, with the emergence of decentralised data storage solutions, such as Solid³, as an alternative to the traditional centralised data silos, new challenges appear as the data subject–data controller roles are still not properly defined in this decentralised contexts. In this context, the creation of Application Programming Interface (API) services would help with the automation of right-related requests as, at their core, they are a ‘request–response’ type of software interface and consequently can be used in different types of software.

Taking this into consideration, this contribution will focus on the following research objectives:

- RO1. Implementing a API method that automates the reply to an access right request, making use of RDF information.
- RO2. Developing a Solid application which uses the implemented method to assist users in the exercising of their right of access in a decentralised storage environment, such as data stored in Solid Pods.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the GDPR’s Data Subject Access Right and its core requirements, Section 3 discusses related work in this area, particularly regarding existing API solutions, Section 4 describes the implementation of an API method that automates the response to an access right request and a Solid application that uses said API method to assist users in exercising their right of access to data stored in Solid Pods and Section 5 presents conclusions and future lines of work.

2. The Right of Access

In an attempt to provide users with more transparency on how their personal data is being processed, GDPR’s right of access puts emphasis not only on the “right to obtain a copy” of said data but also an additional set of information pieces needs to be provided to the subject related with the context in which the processing is made. Therefore, the right of access’s main goal is to give people sufficient and clear information about how their personal data is processed so that subjects know that their data is being handled according with their expectations and its quality is being verified – this will then facilitate the exercise of other rights, such as the right to be forgotten or to rectification. The data subject does not have to provide a justification to request access to the data nor does he need to pay a fee to exercise such right. Unless it is obvious that the request is being made in violation of other regulations, the data controller data has the duty to reply to the data subject’s request. In addition to the requirements specified in GDPR, on January 18th 2022, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB)

²<https://gdpr-info.eu/art-15-gdpr/>

³<https://solidproject.org/>

issued a set of guidelines specifically on the right of access [2]. Table 1 specifies in more detail the information requirements related to GDPR’s right of access.

GDPR provision	Right of Access requirement
Art. 15(1)	Confirmation as to whether or not the controller is processing personal data concerning the requesting person
Art. 15(1)	Access to the personal data concerning the requesting person
Art. 15(1)	Access to the following information on the processing: (a) the purposes of the processing; (b) the categories of personal data; (c) the recipients or categories of recipients; (d) the envisaged duration of the processing or the criteria for determining the duration; (e) the existence of the rights to rectification, erasure, restriction of processing and objection to processing; (f) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority; (g) any available information on the source of the data, if not collected from the data subject; (h) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling.
Art. 15(2)	Information on safeguards pursuant to Art. 46 where the personal data are transferred to a third country or to an international organisation
Art. 15(3)	The obligation of the controller to provide a copy of the personal data undergoing processing
Art.15(3)	Charging of a reasonable fee by the controller based on administrative costs for any further copies requested by the data subject
Art. 15(3)	Provision of information in electronic form
Art. 15(4)	The request should not interfere with the rights and freedoms of others

Table 1. Right of access request requirements and respective GDPR provision.

3. Related Work

There are already a few API implementations specifically targeting the response to data subject right-related requests, however they only focus on providing a copy of the personal data and leave out all the other requirements specified by the GDPR.

Microsoft Graph [3] is a platform developed by Microsoft to access Microsoft 365 data and contains different APIs, such as the ones related with compliance and privacy [4], that can be used to personalize the different services provided by the company and their ecosystem partners. In particular, the Microsoft Graph compliance and privacy APIs were developed to create and manage data subject access requests (DSARs) and to help developers and enterprises to easily identify data subjects and find their personal information. Although the process through which the data is obtained is automated, several components require manual intervention, such as confirmation as to whether the data is being processed, the recipients who have access to that data and so on.

Oracle's Data Privacy API focus on providing a solution for enterprises that use Oracle databases to store personal data to carry out data privacy requests [5]. Currently it supports the implementation of two types of requests, the already discussed Right of Access and also the Right to be forgotten – a right that can be exercised by a data subject when they want the system in question to erase all data related to them.

AppsFlyer [6] goes one step further by providing a API that not only supports access and erasure requests, but also deals with the Right to Data Portability – transfer data from one controller to another – and the Right to Rectification – correct inaccurate data. The request flow in AppsFlyer also involves manual intervention, as when a data subject submits a request, the app owner has to forward the request to AppsFlyer, which then executes the request within 14 days.

Through the analysis of these solutions, it is possible to conclude that there is a gap related to the implementation of an API service that fulfils all the requirements of a GDPR Right of Access request since all solutions only focus on providing a copy of the data and don't provide detailed information regarding purposes for processing, duration of processing and so on.

4. Implementation

In this section, the followed research methodology will be described and the development of a Right of Access API method will be presented as well as the implementation of a Solid application that uses the developed API call to allow Solid users to exercise their right of access to Solid Pod's data.

4.1. Research Methodology

The used methodology approach encompassed the following steps:

1. An evaluation of current gaps on right of access APIs was performed.
2. Similar regulation in different jurisdictions was reviewed in order to understand if new requirements needed to be added into consideration for the implementation of the API.
3. Semantic Web vocabularies were used to specify the information that needs to be provided as they promote data interoperability.
4. The API method and documentation were developed.
5. Solid's personal data storage ecosystem was then chosen to verify the applicability of the API method as it is based on Web standards and specifications.

4.2. API development

The main technologies used to implement the API were the `expressjs`⁴ and `swagger-ui-express`⁵ libraries, used to develop the API and create its respective

⁴<https://expressjs.com/es/>

⁵<https://www.npmjs.com/package/swagger-ui-express>

documentation. Inrupt's JavaScript client libraries⁶ were also used to authenticate the user and to handle data stored in a Solid Pod.

Initially, the developed API only had one parameter which was related to the identity of the user as this is the only requirement described by the GDPR for a data subject to be allowed to exercise their right of access. However, since the data subject may, for example, be interested in accessing only certain categories of data or only accessing data used for a certain purpose, it was decided to add data categories and purposes to the request parameters as in this way the data subject will have a more fine-grained access right.

The main function of the API is to obtain the data stored in the Solid Pod and send it to the user as a JSON file with two components – a boolean variable that will be true in case personal data that matches the request is found in the Pod and a JSON object that contains the respective list of found resources. To enable the access to the data, the user must be logged into their Pod. As previously stated, the authentication protocol is implemented using Inrupt's javascript libraries – a session is generated and stored so that information regarding the identity of the user (present in a WebID profile document in the case of Solid) can be passed to the API request.

Once the user is logged, the API can process an access request. Initially the URI of all resources stored in the Pod is collected and matched with the request. If the request is made without specifying any further parameters, then all the resources present in the Pod will be returned independently of the categories of personal data that they include or the purpose for which its processing is allowed. If a specific set of personal data categories is specified along with the access request then only those categories will be returned. However, it must be noted that for this feature to work, the resources in the Pod need to include a RDF statement, using for instance the Extended Personal Data concepts for DPV⁷, to specify which type of data they contain. Finally, in case the user only wants to access data that is being used for a particular purpose, access control policies that define the purpose for processing the stored resources need to be defined and kept in their Pod. For the purposes of this work, we assume that users are using the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) Profile for Access Control (OAC) [7] to create policies to govern the access to their Solid-stored data⁸. Using these policies the API method matches the request purpose with the stored policies' purposes and if there is a match then the corresponding data is returned. Again, this process also depends on having Solid resources tagged with the personal data category that they contain as purpose-specific policies can be defined for different types of data.

The code of the developed API and respective usage details are available at <https://anonymous.4open.science/r/access-right-api/>.

⁶<https://docs.inrupt.com/developer-tools/javascript/client-libraries/>

⁷<https://w3id.org/dpv/dpv-pd>

⁸The SOPE application available at <https://github.com/besteves4/solid-sope> can be used to automatically generate these policies without having knowledge on ODRL and its semantics.

4.3. Exercising the Right of Access to Solid Pod data

As previously stated, Solid is a protocol focused on providing its users with decentralised personal data storage. Currently, access control to Solid-stored resources is specified using the Web Access Control specification which uses Access Control Lists (ACLs)⁹ to define which agents have access to Solid resources. However, these ACL authorisations don't allow the specification of purposes for the access to the resources as well as not permitting the definition of specific access to particular types of personal data. In this context, as specified in the previous section, this work makes use of OAC policies to overcome this issue. OAC¹⁰ uses the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV), which provides taxonomies for the specification of relevant privacy and data protection information, and ODRL, which allows for the expression of rich policies over digital assets.

As the users need to be able to select specific types of personal data and / or specific purposes for the processing of said data to have a more fine-grained right of access, the developed Solid application includes two drop down trees that use DPV's personal data categories and purposes taxonomies to populate its structure. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate a snapshot of these trees.

Figure 1. Drop down tree of DPV personal data categories.

Figure 2. Drop down tree of DPV purposes.

The selected categories are then used to feed the API request call. An example of a response to a request, and respective information returned, is displayed in Figure 3. For each returned resource, the URI is provided, as well the category

⁹<http://www.w3.org/ns/auth/acl#>

¹⁰<https://w3id.org/oac/>

of personal data included in the file and a list of the policies governing the access to said resource. A download button is also available so that the user can obtain a copy of the resource data.

Figure 3. Example of file returned.

The code of the developed Solid application and respective usage details are available at <https://anonymous.4open.science/r/access-right-solid/>.

This solution provides an advance in relation to the state of the art reviewed solutions as it provides granular information on the personal data categories contained in the resources, as well as the purpose for which it was/can be used, in addition to the provision of a copy of the data.

5. Conclusions

This work explored the implementation of an API service that can be used for the automation of GDPR's Right of Access. Current state of the art solutions developed to assist data subjects and data controllers in the exercising and resolution of data subject right-related requests focus on providing users with the 'right to obtain a copy' of the data but do not fulfil all the requirements set by the GDPR. Furthermore, these APIs are currently not equipped to deal with requests regarding data stored in decentralised systems such as Solid Pods.

Therefore, the main contribution of this work relies on the development of an open source API that can be used in the context of decentralised systems to provide data subjects with a 'fine-grained' right of access where it can be explicitly checked which data is being used for what purpose in addition to obtaining a copy of the data.

In future lines of work, the API can be improved to provide a more complete answer to a Right of Access request – information about other data subject rights

should be provided, as well as clear information regarding recipients of the data. Moreover, theoretically there are factors that have not been considered for the sake of practicality. For example, we have assumed that during the period of time in which the resources are stored in the Pod under the effects of a policy, they can be automatically provided through the API. This feature can also be extended to deal with new policy constraints, such as a limited time duration for the storage or a periodicity constraint. Also, new parameters for filtering the requested data could be added to the API and to the Solid application.

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